

Structural dynamics of pathogenic *ABCC8* single-nucleotide variants and their interactions with gliclazide

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Abstract

Pathogenic single-nucleotide variants (SNVs) in the *ABCC8* gene have been associated with susceptibility to type 2 diabetes (T2D), and understanding how these variants alter protein structure is crucial for the development of personalized therapeutic strategies for T2D. Gliclazide binding to *ABCC8* variants was assessed using molecular docking, 50 ns molecular dynamics simulation (MDS), and MM-PBSA. Docking indicated a conserved pose with affinity shifts; an Arg1144 hydrogen bond persisted in all variants, whereas the wild type (WT) engaged Tyr1293. More favorable docking energies coincided with π - π or π -sulfur contacts involving Trp1296 and Phe591/Tyr1293 or His584. Complexes remained stable during simulation, showing RMSD plateaus, stabilized radius of gyration and solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) after equilibration, and maintained ligand-receptor distances. Phe591Leu showed the most stable profile, whereas Asp1471Asn exhibited deviation. MM-PBSA predicted the strongest binding for the wild type (-21.86 ± 2.70 kcal/mol) and weaker, variant-dependent binding for mutants (-19.46 ± 3.33 to -16.34 ± 2.46 kcal/mol), supporting preserved binding. Experimental validation is required to investigate these variants in K_{ATP} function and clinical response.

Keywords

ABCC8, gliclazide, MM-PBSA, molecular docking, molecular dynamics

Introduction

Genetic variation within and between populations gives rise to diverse phenotypes, often influenced by environmental factors. Single-nucleotide variants (SNVs), the most common form of genetic variation, are widely distributed across the genome and have been extensively charac-

terized. These variants have played a key role in elucidating the genetic architecture of complex diseases, particularly through candidate gene approaches and genome-wide association studies (GWAS) (Zou et al. 2020). In addition, SNVs have been widely used in genomic research to investigate disease mechanisms, evaluate therapeutic responses, and identify genetic risk factors underlying complex

disorders such as type 2 diabetes (T2D) (Yu et al. 2019; Suzuki et al. 2024). T2D is a prevalent and growing metabolic disorder associated with substantial morbidity and mortality worldwide. As of 2021, an estimated 537 million individuals were living with diabetes, with more than 90% of cases attributed to T2D (Sun et al. 2022). The global burden of T2D is expected to increase markedly in the coming decades. T2D is characterized by impaired insulin secretion from pancreatic β -cells and insulin resistance in peripheral tissues. These abnormalities arise from a complex interplay of genetic and environmental factors, including obesity, aging, and physical inactivity (Afraie et al. 2024). Current therapeutic strategies aim to improve insulin sensitivity, enhance insulin secretion, and regulate glucose homeostasis. However, despite the availability of pharmacological agents such as metformin, sulfonylureas, and insulin, treatment outcomes are often limited by secondary failure, adverse effects, and poor patient adherence (Kurniawan et al. 2024).

The *ABCC8* gene encodes sulfonylurea receptor 1 (SUR1), the regulatory subunit of the ATP-sensitive potassium (K_{ATP}) channel, which plays a critical role in insulin secretion. Variants in the *ABCC8* gene can disrupt channel function, leading to dysregulated insulin release. Loss-of-function variants are associated with excessive insulin secretion and hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia (HH), often due to impaired channel opening in response to magnesium-bound ADP (MgADP). In contrast, gain-of-function variants can reduce insulin secretion and contribute to diabetes. While the prevalence of *ABCC8* variants varies across populations and their clinical characteristics remain incompletely understood (Li et al. 2021), recent genomic analyses identified 1,289 T2D-associated SNVs and mapped the *ABCC8* gene to the beta cell-PI cluster, a specific genetic pathway characterized by impaired insulin secretion, elevated glycemic markers (fasting glucose, 2-h glucose, and HbA1c), and decreased proinsulin (Suzuki et al. 2024). A previous study by Elangeeb et al. (2024) investigated T2D-associated variants in the *KCNJ11* gene, which encodes the Kir6.2 core subunit of the K_{ATP} channel. Their molecular dynamics analyses indicated that specific variants (e.g., M199R, R201H, R206H, and Y330H) significantly altered the protein's dynamic behavior, resulting in reduced overall stability, altered residue flexibility, and changes in global compactness compared with the wild-type channel (Elangeeb et al. 2024). While the structural impact of Kir6.2 variants has been explored, how variations in the regulatory SUR1 subunit perturb structural dynamics remains underexplored. Understanding these changes is essential, as SUR1 serves as the primary pharmacological target for sulfonylureas in the treatment of T2D.

Gliclazide, a sulfonylurea with a unique azabicyclo-octyl structure, is widely used in the management of T2D. It exerts its therapeutic effect by binding to SUR1, the regulatory subunit of the K_{ATP} channel encoded by the *ABCC8* gene. This interaction promotes insulin secretion by depolarizing the β -cell membrane and triggering calci-

um influx (Sarkar et al. 2011; Azimi et al. 2023; Sahin et al. 2024). This study aims to employ an *in silico* approach, integrating molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations (MDS), to evaluate the impact of *ABCC8* variants on the binding affinity, structural stability, and potential efficacy of gliclazide. The findings are expected to provide insights into the role of genetic variability in drug response, contributing to the development of personalized therapeutic strategies for T2D.

Materials and methods

Materials

All simulations were performed using a Dell Precision T5820 workstation configured with an Intel Xeon W-2225 processor (4 cores, boost up to 4.6 GHz), 32 GB DDR4 ECC RAM, a 512 GB SSD plus a 2 TB HDD, and an NVIDIA Quadro RTX 4000 GPU (8 GB VRAM); the system ran Windows 10 Professional (64-bit). Additional simulation runs were carried out on an Ubuntu 24.10 desktop equipped with an Intel Core i7-14700F processor (28 cores), 32 GB DDR5 RAM, a 1 TB SSD, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 5070 GPU (12 GB VRAM, 6,144 CUDA cores). Complementary modeling, visualization, and data analysis tasks were performed on a MacBook Pro with an Apple M4 Pro system-on-chip (12-core CPU, 16-core GPU), 24 GB of unified memory, and a 512 GB SSD, running macOS Tahoe 26.2.

Retrieval of *ABCC8* protein sequences and their variants

The wild-type (WT) *ABCC8* protein sequence for *Homo sapiens* (human) was obtained from the UniProt database (<https://www.uniprot.org/>) (Agu et al. 2023), accessed on 24 February 2025. To identify *ABCC8* variants associated with T2D, ClinVar Miner (<https://clinvarminer.genetics.utah.edu/>) (Henrie et al. 2018) was queried on 24 February 2025 using the “variants by condition” search with “T2D,” specifically selecting variants classified as “pathogenic.” Variants with a minimum 2-star review score were selected for further analysis, ensuring reliable evidence for pathogenicity (Harrison et al. 2016). Data from ClinVar Miner were then integrated with corresponding entries from the ClinVar database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/clinvar/>) (Landrum et al. 2018), limited to missense molecular consequences. Finally, only variants supported by at least two stars and multiple submitters were retained for further analysis. To refine the dataset, variants linked to pathological conditions unrelated to T2D were excluded (Keskin Karakoyun et al. 2023). Subsequently, the WT *ABCC8* protein sequence was modified to reflect each identified SNV mutation, enabling the construction of mutant *ABCC8* protein structures (Agu et al. 2023; Kuznetsova et al. 2024).

Protein structure prediction

The three-dimensional (3D) model of the WT ABCC8 protein was generated using the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (<https://alphafold.ebi.ac.uk/>) with its UniProt accession code, Q09428 (Pak et al. 2023). AlphaFold 3 (<https://alphafoldserver.com/>) was used to generate the 3D structures of the mutant ABCC8 proteins, reflecting the specific pathogenic SNVs (Abramson et al. 2024).

Protein model quality check

The 3D models of the ABCC8 protein and its variants were evaluated using the Swiss-Model Structure Assessment server (<https://swissmodel.expasy.org/assess>), employing the Model Quality Estimation (QMEANDisCo) scoring method. QMEANDisCo provides global and per-residue quality estimates based on statistical potentials of mean force, enabling assessment of the model's agreement with experimental structures of similar size (Studer et al. 2020). A QMEANDisCo score above 0.70 was considered indicative of good overall model quality prediction (Guillon et al. 2024). Stereochemical quality was further assessed using MolProbity metrics integrated into Swiss-Model, including the MolProbity score, all-atom clashscore, Ramachandran statistics, and rotamer outliers. These parameters collectively evaluate model geometry and stereochemical correctness. The MolProbity score is a combined single indicator of model quality for protein and nucleic acid structures. It enables comparison of structures across different resolutions. Models with scores lower than the typical range for their resolution require further refinement (Williams et al. 2018).

Preparation of ligand

Two-dimensional (2D) structures of gliclazide (PubChem ID: 3475), metformin (PubChem ID: 4091), and diazoxide (PubChem ID: 3019) were downloaded from PubChem in SDF format (Kim et al. 2023). Metformin was used as a negative control because it lacks the sulfonylurea pharmacophore and is not expected to occupy the SUR1 sulfonylurea pocket, helping to flag nonspecific docking. Diazoxide, a K_{ATP} channel opener that binds SUR1 and functionally opposes sulfonylureas, was included to benchmark pocket selectivity against an antagonist profile and to verify that the model distinguishes openers from blockers. All ligands were converted to 3D and geometry-optimized in Chem3D Ultra v22 (PerkinElmer Informatics 2022) using MM2 energy minimization to relieve steric strain and refine bond lengths and angles (Alotaib and Dermawan 2025). Energy minimization was performed with default Chem3D parameters.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking was performed with High Ambiguity Driven DOCKing v2.4 (HADDOCK, <https://rascar.science.uu.nl/haddock2.4/>), accessed on 5 August 2025

(Honorato et al. 2021, 2024). Putative ligand-binding pockets on ABCC8 were predicted with P2Rank (<https://prankweb.cz/>) by selecting the AlphaFold structure option and inputting the UniProt ID (Krivák and Hoksza 2018). The top-ranked pocket residue list was exported and used to define the active-site restraints for HADDOCK. Docked poses were ranked primarily by the HADDOCK score (more negative values indicate better solutions), with the best cluster selected based on the lowest average score and favorable interface energy (Deshpande et al. 2023). Protein binding energy prediction (PRODIGY-LIGAND, <https://rascar.science.uu.nl/prodigy/lig>) (Kurkcuoglu et al. 2018; Vangone et al. 2019) was applied to the top poses to predict binding free energies (ΔG , kcal/mol) to estimate binding strength. More negative ΔG values indicate stronger predicted interactions (Syahbanu et al. 2021). Visualization was performed using BIOVIA Discovery Studio (2D interaction diagrams) and UCSF ChimeraX version 1.11 (3D structures) (Meng et al. 2023).

Molecular dynamics simulation (MDS)

MDS was conducted with GROMACS 2024.3 (Abraham et al. 2024) to evaluate the dynamic behavior, structural stability, and binding interactions of the most stable ligand-receptor complex. Ligand topologies were prepared using the GAFF2 force field, and AmberTools21 (ACPYPE module) was used to assign atomic partial charges using the AM1-BCC method (Jakalian et al. 2002; Sousa da Silva and Vranken 2012; He et al. 2020). The protein structures were parameterized using the CHARMM27 force field. The protein-ligand complex was placed in a truncated octahedral box with a buffer distance of at least 1.2 nm from the solute to the box boundary and solvated with TIP3P water molecules. Ligand and receptor coordinates were merged and verified in UCSF Chimera, after which the topology files were refined to ensure proper inclusion of ligand parameters. The solvated systems were neutralized and adjusted to 150 mM NaCl to mimic physiological ionic conditions (Jó-járt and Martinek 2007; Kerns et al. 2015). Periodic boundary conditions (PBCs) were applied to mimic continuous biological environments. Short-range nonbonded interactions were cut off at 1.0 nm, while long-range electrostatic forces were calculated using the particle mesh Ewald (PME) method (Essmann et al. 1995; Musliha et al. 2024).

Energy minimization was carried out using the conjugate gradient method until the forces fell below 500 kJ/mol/nm. Two equilibration phases followed: first, an NVT equilibration for 200 ps at 310 K using the V-rescale thermostat, and then an NPT equilibration for 200 ps at 1 atm with the Monte Carlo barostat. The production run was conducted for 50 ns without restraints, using the Nosé-Hoover thermostat and Parrinello-Rahman barostat to maintain accurate temperature and pressure. These simulation protocols were adapted from Ke et al. (2022) and Ridruejo et al. (2025) and applied to the present protein-ligand system (Ke et al. 2022; Ridruejo et al. 2025). The resulting trajectories were analyzed using root-mean-square deviation (RMSD),

root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF), radius of gyration (RoG), solvent-accessible surface area (SASA), and hydrogen-bond analysis to evaluate complex stability, flexibility, compactness, exposure, and interaction strength throughout the simulation (Borjian Boroujeni et al. 2021).

Molecular mechanics–Poisson–Boltzmann surface area (MM-PBSA) calculations

The binding free energy between the ligand and its target receptor was estimated using the MM-PBSA method implemented in the `gmx_MMPBSA` package version 1.6.4 (Valdés-Tresanco et al. 2021). Energy calculations were based on trajectory data obtained from the 50 ns molecular dynamics (MD) production phase, with snapshots extracted at uniform time intervals to ensure representative sampling of the system's equilibrium state. The MM-PBSA model considered four major energy components: van der Waals, electrostatic, polar solvation, and nonpolar solvation energies. Nonpolar contributions were evaluated using the solvent-accessible surface area (SASA) approach. Default dielectric constants and grid spacing parameters optimized for protein–ligand systems were employed to achieve a balanced trade-off between computational efficiency and accuracy.

Results

ABCC8 protein sequences and their variants

The WT ABCC8 protein sequence was retrieved from the UniProt database. This sequence was later used to introduce the SNVs identified from the databases. SNVs were obtained from ClinVar Miner and the ClinVar database. A total of 18 T2D-associated variants were identified and used to generate mutant ABCC8 protein sequences for structural modeling. Table 1 lists these T2D-associated variants. Population allele frequencies (minor allele frequency; MAF) were retrieved from the Genome Aggregation Database (<https://gnomad.broadinstitute.org/>) (gnomAD, version 4.1.1) (Karczewski et al. 2020) or dbSNP (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/snp/>) (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism Database; Sherry et al. 2001). Clinical significance, associated disease phenotypes, and available genetic segregation data were obtained by querying the ClinVar database (NCBI). All database queries were conducted between 21 and 29 April 2026.

Protein structure prediction and quality check

The 3D structure of the WT ABCC8 protein was successfully retrieved from the AlphaFold Protein Structure Database (UniProt accession: Q09428). Mutant ABCC8 protein models reflecting 18 SNVs were generated using AlphaFold 3. All predicted models were obtained without missing regions and were suitable for downstream quality assessment. The structural quality of the ABCC8 WT and mutant

protein models was evaluated using QMEANDisCo and MolProbity metrics within the Swiss-Model Structure Assessment server (Table 2). Model quality was evaluated against established structural benchmarks: a QMEANDisCo score > 0.6 for reliable modeling (Studer et al. 2020); a MolProbity score < 2.0 and clashscore < 5.0 for high-resolution stereochemical accuracy (Williams et al. 2018); and > 90% of residues in Ramachandran favored regions to confirm backbone acceptability (Laskowski et al. 1993).

The WT ABCC8 structure achieved a QMEANDisCo global score of 0.73 ± 0.05 , a MolProbity score of 1.33, and a clashscore of 1.67. Ramachandran statistics showed 95.69% of residues in favored regions, 1.39% in outlier regions, and 1.39% rotamer outliers. For the 18 SNVs, QMEANDisCo scores were consistent with the WT ($0.72\text{--}0.74 \pm 0.05$). MolProbity scores remained acceptable (1.88–2.29), while clashscores were slightly higher than the WT (8.25–12.7), reflecting minor variations in atomic contacts. Ramachandran favored residues remained high across all variants (95.50–97.02%), alongside low Ramachandran outliers (< 1.4%) and rotamer outliers (1.61–3.07%). These metrics confirm the structural integrity and suitability of both the WT and mutant models for downstream molecular docking and molecular dynamics simulations.

The prepared ligands and molecular docking results

The ligands gliclazide, metformin, and diazoxide were successfully retrieved and converted into 3D structures. Their geometries were optimized using MM2 energy minimization, yielding stable conformations. The optimized ligands were then used for subsequent docking simulations. The molecular docking results are presented in Table 3, with detailed binding energies and interaction profiles provided in Suppl. materials 1, 2. Ligand ranking was consistent across the WT and all mutant models, with gliclazide showing the strongest binding, followed by diazoxide and metformin as the weakest. Gliclazide displayed the most favorable profile ($\Delta G \approx -7$ kcal/mol, large buried surface area (BSA), and highly favorable HADDOCK scores); diazoxide showed intermediate binding ($\Delta G \approx -6$ to -7 kcal/mol), while metformin exhibited weaker binding ($\Delta G \approx -5$ kcal/mol, small BSA). Some mutations appeared to induce minor shifts in binding affinity. For example, the Arg526Cys mutation slightly enhanced gliclazide binding, while the Arg1436Gln mutation modestly improved metformin binding, although not enough to surpass diazoxide or gliclazide. Among the mutants, several gliclazide complexes exhibited favorable performance, including Arg526Cys–gliclazide, Asp1471Asn–gliclazide, Arg74Gln–gliclazide, Glu128Lys–gliclazide, and Phe591Leu–gliclazide. These variants were selected based on their highly negative predicted binding free energies (ΔG). However, some differences in HADDOCK scores were observed, indicating a trade-off between binding affinity and docking stability. Figs 1, 2 present the 2D interaction diagrams and 3D visualizations of these selected complexes, alongside those of the WT complexes.

Table 1. List of *ABCC8* variants associated with T2D.

Name (HGVS)	rsID	Protein change	Population frequency (MAF)	Functional consequence	Segregation data	Clinical context	References
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.96C>G (p.Asn32Lys)	rs2496930134	N32K	0.0000007	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (biallelic/compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; familial hyperinsulinism	ElSheikh et al. 2025
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.4238C>T (p.Pro1413Leu)	rs1436692401	P1412L, P1413L, P1414L, P1435L	0.000001282	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (autosomal recessive inheritance)	Type 2 diabetes; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia; hereditary hyperinsulinemic	Velde et al. 2025
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.1332G>T (p.Gln444His)	rs760062120	Q443H, Q444H	0.000006196	Loss of function	Observed to segregate with disease in related individuals	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia; familial hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia	Krivova et al. 2025
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.4253G>A (p.Arg1418His)	rs1446306735	R1418H, R1419H, R1417H, R1440H	0.000003203	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia; familial hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia	Li et al. 2021
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.1576C>T (p.Arg526Cys)	rs751279984	R526C, R525C	0.00002293	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Arya et al. 2014
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.3544C>T (p.Arg1182Trp)	rs797045209	R1182W, R1183W, R1204W, R1181W	0.000001859	Gain of function	<i>De novo</i> occurrence in multiple affected individuals	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia; MODY	Scala et al. 2025
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.382G>A (p.Glu128Lys)	rs781617345	E128K	0.000003717	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Yan et al. 2007
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.4628T>C (p.Leu1543Pro)	rs72559713	L1543P, L1544P, L1565P, L1542P	0.00001512	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Taschenberger et al. 2002
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.62T>A (p.Val21Asp)	rs200670692	V21D	0.00000348	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Martin et al. 2016
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.3640C>T (p.Arg1214Trp)	rs139964066	R1214W, R1215W, R1213W, R1236W	0.00003841	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (compound heterozygous)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism	Rozenkova et al. 2015
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.331G>A (p.Gly111Arg)	rs761749884	G111R	0.000006196	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Fernández-Marmiesse et al. 2006
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.3641G>A (p.Arg1214Gln)	rs367850779	R1214Q, R1215Q, R1213Q, R1236Q	0.00001239	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Yan et al. 2007
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.4307G>A (p.Arg1436Gln)	rs387906407	R1436Q, R1437Q, R1435Q, R1458Q	0.000007742	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism	Tanizawa et al. 2000
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.220C>T (p.Arg74Trp)	rs201682634	R74W	0.000005576	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Fernández-Marmiesse et al. 2006
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.221G>A (p.Arg74Gln)	rs72559734	R74Q	0.000004956	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (homozygous/compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism	Kwak et al. 2016
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.4411G>A (p.Asp1471Asn)	rs72559716	D1471N, D1472N, D1493N, D1470N	0.00001465	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (heterozygous/compound heterozygous in trans)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes; leucine-induced hypoglycemia	Bohnen et al. 2018
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.4432G>A (p.Gly1478Arg)	rs72559715	G1478R, G1479R, G1477R, G1500R	0.0000006195	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (heterozygous/autosomal dominant)	Type 2 diabetes; hereditary hyperinsulinism; neonatal diabetes	Pinney et al. 2008
NM_000352.6(AB-CC8):c.1773C>G (p.Phe591Leu)	rs72559726	F590L, F591L	0.0000	Loss of function	Observed in affected individuals (heterozygous/autosomal dominant)	Not provided	Shyng et al. 1998

Table 2. *ABCC8* protein model quality assessment.

Protein	QMEANDisCo	MolProbity score	Clashscore	Ramachandran favored (%)	Ramachandran outliers (%)	Rotamer outliers (%)
<i>ABCC8</i> WT	0.73 ± 0.05	1.33	1.67	95.69	1.39	1.39
Asn32Lys	0.74 ± 0.05	1.93	9.12	96.07	0.70	1.68
Arg74Gln	0.74 ± 0.05	1.93	8.53	96.33	0.57	1.97
Arg74Trp	0.74 ± 0.05	1.88	10.20	97.02	0.38	1.75
Arg526Cys	0.74 ± 0.05	1.95	8.97	95.88	0.95	1.75
Arg1182Trp	0.73 ± 0.05	1.96	10.59	96.58	0.38	1.83
Arg1214Gln	0.73 ± 0.05	2.03	9.44	95.69	0.95	2.05
Arg1214Trp	0.73 ± 0.05	1.98	9.32	95.69	1.33	1.75
Arg1418His	0.73 ± 0.05	1.94	10.79	96.83	0.25	1.83
Arg1436Gln	0.74 ± 0.05	1.93	8.25	95.95	0.95	1.83
Asp1471Asn	0.74 ± 0.05	1.88	8.57	96.14	0.63	1.61
Gln444His	0.73 ± 0.05	1.99	10.51	96.39	0.51	1.90
Glu128Lys	0.74 ± 0.05	1.91	10.23	96.83	0.44	1.75
Gly111Arg	0.73 ± 0.05	1.94	8.76	95.50	1.01	1.61
Gly1478Arg	0.73 ± 0.05	1.93	8.88	96.01	0.57	1.75
Leu1543Pro	0.73 ± 0.05	2.00	9.17	95.50	0.70	1.83
Pro1413Leu	0.74 ± 0.05	1.95	9.04	96.07	0.57	1.83
Val21Asp	0.73 ± 0.05	1.95	10.40	96.39	0.38	1.68
Phe591Leu	0.72 ± 0.06	2.29	12.70	95.63	1.14	3.07

Molecular dynamics results

MDS was conducted to evaluate the interaction and stability of the studied complexes. MDS analysis is provided in Fig. 3. RMSD (Fig. 3A) was used to assess overall structural stability. Across the 50 ns simulations, most complexes exhibited an initial rise during the early phase (0–10 ns) and then fluctuated around a plateau, indicating equilibration without continuous drift. The WT–gliclazide complex, used as a positive control, maintained stable behavior with a mean RMSD of 0.64 ± 0.13 nm. Among the most stable complexes, Arg74Gln–gliclazide (0.36 ± 0.04 nm), Arg526Cys–gliclazide (0.51 ± 0.12 nm), and Phe591Leu–gliclazide (0.32 ± 0.04 nm) showed the lowest and most consistent RMSD profiles, suggesting the highest overall structural stability. In contrast, Asp1471Asn–gliclazide displayed the largest deviations (0.92 ± 0.30 nm) and a pronounced late increase toward the end of the trajectory, reaching approximately 1.6–1.8 nm at approximately 47–50 ns, indicating the least stable behavior, while WT–metformin also exhibited comparatively elevated RMSD values (0.87 ± 0.17 nm), consistent with greater conformational variability.

Fig. 3B shows the RMSF, which reflects the flexibility of individual amino acid residues throughout the simulation. Overall, the trajectories exhibited low baseline fluctuations for most residues, indicating that the protein core remained generally stable across complexes. At the same time, pronounced mobility was confined to several discrete regions, consistent with flexible loop/terminal segments. The mean RMSF values were relatively similar across most complexes, ranging from 0.17 to 0.27 nm. The WT–gliclazide complex showed a moderate mean RMSF (0.18 nm), supporting overall stable dynamics relative to the more flexible variants. The lowest mean RMSF values were observed for WT–diazoxide (0.17 nm) and

Phe591Leu–gliclazide (0.18 nm), suggesting the most rigid residue-wise behavior, whereas Arg526Cys–gliclazide (0.27 nm) and Glu128Lys–gliclazide (0.24 nm) displayed the highest mean RMSF values, indicating increased overall flexibility. Notably, the major fluctuation peaks in the RMSF profiles occurred outside the predefined docking pocket residues (547–591, 1022–1067, 1140–1148, and 1285–1300), suggesting that the observed flexibility was primarily associated with non-pocket regions rather than directly reflecting instability at the ligand-binding site.

The compactness of each complex was assessed using the RoG (Fig. 3C). Overall, the complexes showed relatively narrow RoG fluctuations, with a slight reduction during the early phase followed by stabilization, indicating that the global fold remained compact without pronounced expansion. The WT–gliclazide complex maintained a stable RoG profile, with a mean RoG of 4.30 ± 0.02 nm, supporting consistent structural compactness over time. Phe591Leu–gliclazide exhibited the lowest mean RoG (4.21 ± 0.02 nm), indicating the most compact conformation, followed by WT–metformin (4.24 ± 0.02 nm). In contrast, Arg526Cys–gliclazide showed the highest mean RoG (4.35 ± 0.03 nm). SASA analysis (Fig. 3D) was used to assess solvent exposure of each complex. Overall, all complexes showed an apparent decrease in SASA during the initial phase (approximately 0–10 ns), followed by stabilization, indicating progressive burial of surface area and a generally stable global fold. The WT–gliclazide complex maintained relatively steady solvent exposure, with a mean SASA of 755.69 ± 17.33 nm². Phe591Leu–gliclazide exhibited the lowest mean SASA (721.79 ± 20.49 nm²), suggesting the most compact/least solvent-exposed conformation, whereas Arg526Cys–gliclazide showed the highest mean SASA (765.59 ± 23.07 nm²), suggesting a more solvent-exposed and less compact ensemble.

Figure 1. 2D interaction diagrams of selected ABCC8 variant-gliclazide complexes alongside the wild-type (WT) complexes. A. WT-gliclazide; B. WT-metformin; C. WT-diazoxide; D. Arg526Cys-gliclazide; E. Asp1471Asn-gliclazide; F. Arg74Gln-gliclazide; G. Glu128Lys-gliclazide; H. Phe591Leu-gliclazide.

Figure 2. 3D visualizations of selected *ABCC8* variant–gliclizide complexes alongside the wild-type (WT) complexes. **A.** WT–gliclizide; **B.** WT–metformin; **C.** WT–diazoxide; **D.** Arg526Cys–gliclizide; **E.** Asp1471Asn–gliclizide; **F.** Arg74Gln–gliclizide; **G.** Glu128Lys–gliclizide; **H.** Phe591Leu–gliclizide.

Figure 3. MDS analysis. **A.** RMSD; **B.** RMSF; **C.** RoG; **D.** SASA; **E.** Distance; **F.** Number of H-bonds. The analyses were performed for the following complexes: WT-diazoxide, WT-gliclazide, WT-metformin, Arg74Gln-gliclazide, Arg526Cys-gliclazide, Asp1471Asn-gliclazide, Glu128Lys-gliclazide, and Phe591Leu-gliclazide.

Fig. 3E shows the positional stability of the ligand within the binding site during the 50 ns simulation, as assessed by the average distance between the ligand and receptor centers of mass. Most complexes fluctuated within a relatively narrow distance range after an initial adjustment, suggesting that the ligands generally remained associated with the receptor throughout the production run. The WT-gliclazide complex maintained a stable distance, with

a mean value of 2.77 ± 0.17 nm. Asp1471Asn-gliclazide showed the lowest mean distance (2.33 ± 0.23 nm), indicating the closest average ligand-receptor proximity, whereas WT-metformin exhibited the highest mean distance (3.11 ± 0.23 nm), consistent with a larger separation. Phe591Leu-gliclazide displayed the lowest variability (2.68 ± 0.04 nm), indicating the most consistent ligand positioning over time, while the remaining complexes

Table 3. Molecular docking results of ligands with WT and mutant ABCC8 protein complexes.

Complex name	Binding affinity ΔG (kcal/mol) PRODIGY	ΔG_{score} PRODIGY	HADDOCK score
WT-metformin	-5.00	188.48	-12.8 \pm 0.9
WT-gliclazide	-7.24	146.14	-30.4 \pm 2.4
WT-diazoxide	-6.83	151.41	-18.6 \pm 1.1
Asn32Lys-metformin	-5.23	181.42	-12.1 \pm 2.5
Asn32Lys-gliclazide	-7.36	142.46	-26.8 \pm 6.3
Asn32Lys-diazoxide	-6.27	167.07	-19.6 \pm 1.9
Arg74Gln-metformin	-5.06	186.24	-13.0 \pm 1.8
Arg74Gln-gliclazide	-7.44	140.66	-30.3 \pm 2.1
Arg74Gln-diazoxide	-6.24	166.80	-17.7 \pm 1.3
Arg74Trp-metformin	-4.78	195.21	-11.8 \pm 3.0
Arg74Trp-gliclazide	-7.11	147.11	-19.4 \pm 2.1
Arg74Trp-diazoxide	-6.98	147.65	-16.9 \pm 0.8
Arg526Cys-metformin	-5.12	184.84	-16.1 \pm 0.8
Arg526Cys-gliclazide	-7.30	142.03	-32.1 \pm 1.1
Arg526Cys-diazoxide	-6.31	166.06	-18.2 \pm 2.1
Arg1182Trp-metformin	-5.00	188.58	-10.7 \pm 0.9
Arg1182Trp-gliclazide	-6.99	153.02	-21.1 \pm 1.9
Arg1182Trp-diazoxide	-6.96	148.89	-16.1 \pm 2.2
Arg1214Gln-metformin	-5.24	181.05	-17.0 \pm 2.3
Arg1214Gln-gliclazide	-7.30	143.81	-25.0 \pm 4.9
Arg1214Gln-diazoxide	-6.60	157.88	-14.3 \pm 1.5
Arg1214Trp-metformin	-4.91	190.59	-12.2 \pm 2.0
Arg1214Trp-gliclazide	-7.38	141.13	-26.2 \pm 3.1
Arg1214Trp-diazoxide	-6.29	166.24	-19.7 \pm 0.9
Arg1418His-metformin	-5.04	187.37	-10.4 \pm 2.7
Arg1418His-gliclazide	-6.88	155.33	-19.9 \pm 1.4
Arg1418His-diazoxide	-6.55	158.88	-16.7 \pm 0.7
Arg1436Gln-metformin	-5.86	163.49	-13.3 \pm 1.5
Arg1436Gln-gliclazide	-7.22	146.03	-24.4 \pm 2.6
Arg1436Gln-diazoxide	-6.34	162.78	-18.6 \pm 1.4
Asp1471Asn-metformin	-4.86	192.20	-12.4 \pm 1.3
Asp1471Asn-gliclazide	-7.35	142.21	-30.7 \pm 1.7
Asp1471Asn-diazoxide	-6.14	170.22	-18.8 \pm 1.5
Gln444His-metformin	-4.63	198.94	-12.5 \pm 2.4
Gln444His-gliclazide	-7.20	146.14	-21.7 \pm 4.0
Gln444His-diazoxide	-6.68	156.34	-18.9 \pm 0.5
Glu128Lys-metformin	-5.08	186.25	-11.6 \pm 3.1
Glu128Lys-gliclazide	-7.47	139.27	-28.2 \pm 2.4
Glu128Lys-diazoxide	-6.28	165.89	-17.6 \pm 4.7
Gly111Arg-metformin	-5.51	173.10	-14.2 \pm 4.1
Gly111Arg-gliclazide	-7.28	144.05	-30.0 \pm 3.9
Gly111Arg-diazoxide	-6.21	166.99	-20.4 \pm 1.5
Gly1478Arg-metformin	-5.18	183.21	-13.9 \pm 1.4
Gly1478Arg-gliclazide	-7.17	148.29	-27.6 \pm 3.1
Gly1478Arg-diazoxide	-6.12	170.70	-15.9 \pm 0.8
Leu1543Pro-metformin	-5.31	179.40	-13.7 \pm 2.8
Leu1543Pro-gliclazide	-7.21	145.73	-28.9 \pm 2.5
Leu1543Pro-diazoxide	-6.30	165.85	-21.0 \pm 1.1
Pro1413Leu-metformin	-5.25	181.32	-15.6 \pm 2.5
Pro1413Leu-gliclazide	-7.05	150.74	-28.6 \pm 3.0
Pro1413Leu-diazoxide	-6.41	164.07	-22.8 \pm 1.2
Val21Asp-metformin	-4.99	188.55	-15.8 \pm 4.5
Val21Asp-gliclazide	-7.46	140.20	-23.3 \pm 6.9
Val21Asp-diazoxide	-7.07	145.83	-23.3 \pm 6.9
Phe591Leu-metformin	-4.98	187.97	-22.7 \pm 1.4
Phe591Leu-gliclazide	-7.95	130.42	-30.3 \pm 4.1
Phe591Leu-diazoxide	-6.80	154.41	-27.1 \pm 0.6

showed intermediate mean distances ranging from 2.54 to 2.77 nm with modest fluctuations.

Hydrogen-bond analysis (Fig. 3F) was performed to evaluate the persistence of polar interactions between the ligand and receptor during the 50 ns simulation. Overall, the complexes formed a variable number of hydrogen bonds over time. The WT-gliclazide complex showed a relatively low mean H-bond number of 0.51 ± 0.63 , indicating that direct hydrogen bonds were present only intermittently during the trajectory. Phe591Leu-gliclazide exhibited the highest and most sustained H-bonding, with a mean of 2.67 ± 0.67 (maximum 6), suggesting more substantial and more persistent polar contacts, which can contribute to improved binding affinity and stability. WT-metformin also showed comparatively higher H-bonding (1.61 ± 1.07 , maximum 6), but with a more fluctuating interaction pattern over time. Arg526Cys-gliclazide exhibited the lowest mean H-bond number (0.19 ± 0.44).

MM-PBSA calculations

The MM/PBSA binding free energy ($\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$) values for all complexes are summarized in Table 4. The WT-gliclazide complex showed the most favorable binding free energy (-21.86 ± 2.70 kcal/mol). In contrast, WT-diazoxide (-10.00 ± 3.20 kcal/mol) and WT-metformin (-9.34 ± 2.17 kcal/mol) exhibited substantially less favorable binding energies. For the mutant complexes, Arg74Gln-gliclazide displayed the most favorable $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ (-19.46 ± 3.33 kcal/mol), followed by Phe591Leu-gliclazide (-18.95 ± 4.93 kcal/mol) and Asp1471Asn-gliclazide (-18.18 ± 3.09 kcal/mol). The remaining mutants, Arg526Cys-gliclazide (-16.86 ± 3.81 kcal/mol) and Glu128Lys-gliclazide (-16.34 ± 2.46 kcal/mol), showed comparatively less favorable binding energies among the mutant group.

Table 4. MM-PBSA binding free energy results for selected ABCC8 variant-gliclazide complexes alongside the wild-type (WT) complexes.

Complex	MM-PBSA free binding energy $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ (kcal/mol)
WT-Diazoxide	-10.00 \pm 3.20
WT-Gliclazide	-21.86 \pm 2.70
WT-Metformin	-9.34 \pm 2.17
Arg74Gln-Gliclazide	-19.46 \pm 3.33
Arg526Cys-Gliclazide	-16.86 \pm 3.81
Asp1471Asn-Gliclazide	-18.18 \pm 3.09
Glu128Lys-Gliclazide	-16.34 \pm 2.46
Phe591Leu-Gliclazide	-18.95 \pm 4.93

Discussion

Molecular docking is a computational method used to predict the ability of molecules to interact with a protein's binding site under static conditions (Tjandrawinata et al. 2024). Docking results are typically assessed based on changes in Gibbs free energy (ΔG), which reflect the thermodynamic favorability of the interaction. A lower ΔG

indicates a more stable and favorable binding interaction (Syahbanu et al. 2021). Protein–ligand binding generally occurs when ΔG is negative at equilibrium under constant pressure and temperature, similar to spontaneous processes (Du et al. 2016). Binding affinity thresholds help classify interaction strengths: ΔG values below -4.25 kcal/mol suggest potential binding, below -5.00 kcal/mol indicate good binding strength, and below -7.00 kcal/mol signify satisfactory binding strength (Liu et al. 2021). In this study, molecular docking revealed that gliclazide had strong binding affinity ($\Delta G \approx -7$ kcal/mol) and diazoxide exhibited good to satisfactory binding ($\Delta G \approx -6$ to -7 kcal/mol), while metformin showed potential for good binding ($\Delta G \approx -4$ to -5 kcal/mol). The HADDOCK scoring function combines multiple energetic components (van der Waals, electrostatic, desolvation, among others) along with the BSA. A more negative overall score for a mutant indicates a more optimized ligand–protein interface. Accordingly, the rank order of HADDOCK scores across variants provides a helpful summary of binding affinity differences, consistent with the ΔG predictions (Computational Structural Biology group 2025).

The docking results show that gliclazide–mutant complexes generally exhibit satisfactory binding. While specific mutations cause minor shifts in binding affinity, they do not significantly alter the overall drug ranking. This suggests that mutations in *ABCC8* may slightly influence drug binding, but gliclazide consistently remains the most stable and reliable binder, even in the presence of mutations. The 2D interaction diagrams (Fig. 1) provide an overview of the ligand–receptor interaction in a single representative pose. Therefore, the interpretation was considered alongside the HADDOCK/PRODIGY scores before further MD simulation analysis. Gliclazide was found to bind in a conserved pose anchored by a hydrogen bond to Arg1144 across all mutants, whereas in the wild type, it binds to Tyr1293. Additionally, an Asn547 H-bond appears in some of the mutants. Variants differ mainly in aromatic/soft contacts, namely the presence of π – π (stacked or T-shaped) and π –sulfur interactions, which are typically with Trp1296, Phe591/Tyr1293, or His584 and correlate with slightly more negative ΔG , whereas complexes lacking these rely on alkyl/ π – σ contacts and score modestly worse. The strongest complex (Phe591Leu, $\Delta G -7.95$) retains the Arg1144 anchor and a π – π contact to Trp1296, indicating that aromatic compensation can offset residue changes, while overall binding remains resilient across mutants.

Docking produces a single, static snapshot of a putative binding pose and may therefore overlook mutation-driven effects that emerge from changes in binding dynamics. MDS-complemented docking can reveal how mutations influence the stability, flexibility, and persistence of key protein–ligand interactions by capturing time-dependent behavior, even when the docked conformations appear similar (Pantsar and Poso 2018). In this study, MDS was performed to support the docking results and was combined with MM-PBSA analysis to estimate binding energetics. By introducing explicit time and atomic mo-

tion, MDS enables the protein and ligand to adjust continuously, providing a more realistic view of the complex and offering additional insight into binding stability, potential unbinding pathways, and kinetic behavior (Souza et al. 2021). This approach is beneficial for identifying mutation-induced instabilities, such as those arising from SNV-related perturbations at the binding interface. MM-PBSA is a widely used end-state free energy method that estimates binding free energy by combining molecular mechanics energy terms with an implicit solvation model (Martínez-Muñoz et al. 2017). Negative $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values indicate that complex formation is energetically favorable, reflecting stronger binding affinity (Musliha et al. 2024).

Lower RMSD values indicate a more stable protein–ligand complex. RMSF reflects the average fluctuation of residues during the simulation and provides insight into local flexibility. RoG describes overall compactness: lower RoG values suggest a more compact complex, whereas higher RoG values may indicate loosening of the structure and potential ligand dissociation. SASA values generally correspond to a more exposed and less stable structure. A lower value of the water–residue connectivity metric indicates a denser network of interactions between water molecules and amino acid residues (Nahar et al. 2024). In this study, MDS results suggest that most *ABCC8* SNVs did not destabilize gliclazide binding within the 50 ns run time, as indicated by plateaued RMSD profiles, stable RoG/SASA trends after equilibration, and generally maintained ligand–receptor distances. Among the variants, Phe591Leu showed the most favorable interaction pattern, combining high global stability with consistent ligand positioning and more persistent hydrogen bonding, supporting a more stable bound state relative to the WT control. In contrast, Asp1471Asn exhibited a pronounced late structural deviation, indicating that this SNV is the most likely to perturb complex stability during the simulation. RMSF peaks were largely outside the predefined pocket residues, suggesting that observed flexibility is primarily associated with non-pocket regions rather than direct disruption of the binding site.

According to the MM-PBSA analysis (Table 4), the more negative the value, the greater the complex's stability. In this study, WT–gliclazide showed the most favorable predicted binding free energy (-21.86 ± 2.70 kcal/mol), supporting stronger affinity relative to the other ligands and mutant–gliclazide complexes. In comparison, all SNVs bound gliclazide with less favorable (less negative) $\Delta G_{\text{binding}}$ values (ranging from -19.46 ± 3.33 to -16.34 ± 2.46 kcal/mol), suggesting that these substitutions may moderately weaken the predicted binding affinity vs. the WT control. When considered alongside the MD stability metrics, these findings indicate that some variants (e.g., Phe591Leu) can maintain a stable bound pose yet still display a slightly less favorable MM-PBSA ΔG , highlighting that structural stability and predicted binding free energy do not always correlate perfectly due to the approximate nature of MM-PBSA and contributions not fully captured. Overall, *ABCC8* variants did not abolish gliclazide binding *in silico*. Still, they modulated binding stability

and predicted affinity in a variant-dependent manner, with Phe591Leu showing the most stable interaction profile and Asp1471Asn showing the greatest destabilization.

Sulfonylureas act by binding SUR1 and inhibiting K_{ATP} channels; therefore, variants that alter the SUR1 mechanism may influence this drug–receptor interaction. The Phe591Leu variant in ABCC8/SUR1 is a missense mutation associated with persistent hyperinsulinemic hypoglycemia of infancy (PHHI). Although functional K_{ATP} channels can still form, this variant disrupts channel regulation. Phe591Leu channels show a markedly reduced response to diazoxide, a K_{ATP} opener. Because diazoxide and sulfonylureas, including gliclazide, used in this study, both act on SUR1 but drive K_{ATP} gating in opposite directions, reduced diazoxide sensitivity suggests altered SUR1 conformational coupling that could also affect sulfonylurea-mediated channel closure and gliclazide responsiveness (Shyng et al. 1998). The Asp1471Asn variant, which showed the least favorable profile in this study's simulations, has been reported to cause congenital hyperinsulinism (CHI). Instead of trafficking to the cell surface to regulate insulin secretion, mutant channel complexes may be retained in the endoplasmic reticulum (ER), likely due to impaired folding or reduced stability, leading to subsequent recognition by ER quality-control mechanisms. This suggests that Asp1471Asn could reduce the availability of functional SUR1/ K_{ATP} channels at the plasma membrane, potentially altering sulfonylurea responsiveness by decreasing the amount of drug-accessible target and disrupting normal channel regulation (Muzyamba et al. 2007). Molecular docking and MDS primarily evaluate how a ligand binds to an already folded protein and how stable that complex remains over time. These approaches can indicate whether variants may alter binding geometry or local dynamics. Still, they cannot directly capture cellular trafficking problems such as ER retention, a point that experimental data must support. As a future direction, the predicted variant-dependent differences in gliclazide interaction can be validated *in vitro* by expressing WT and mutant SUR1/ K_{ATP} channels and quantifying sulfonylurea sensitivity using electrophysiological

recordings (e.g., patch-clamp) to derive concentration–response relationships (IC_{50}) (Proks et al. 2018). Nevertheless, the present study uses MD to assess whether ABCC8 variants influence the binding stability of gliclazide.

Conclusion

These results suggest that gliclazide is a relatively robust therapeutic agent, as its predicted binding to ABCC8 is not substantially affected by the examined variants. However, docking-derived binding energies alone are insufficient to determine the physiological consequences of these variants. Functional studies of K_{ATP} channel activity, along with clinical data from affected individuals, are required to establish whether specific ABCC8 SNVs disrupt glucose homeostasis through K_{ATP} channel dysfunction. Additionally, the simulations assumed homomeric mutant channel assemblies, which may not fully capture the structural complexity of heteromeric channels present in patients with compound heterozygous mutations.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

Regarding the use of AI in the preparation of this manuscript, the authors declare the following:

AI tools were used to support manuscript preparation. ChatGPT assisted with language polishing and improving the clarity of technical writing. All AI-assisted text was carefully reviewed and edited by the authors, who take full responsibility for the content. All interpretations, conclusions, and final editorial decisions presented in this article were made by the authors.

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Author contributions

Stefeny Theresia Simatupang: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Visualization, Writing – original draft; Doni Dermawan: Data curation, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; Nadia: Writing – review & editing; Santi Tan: Supervision, Writing – review & editing; Adi Yulandi: Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing; Raymond Rubianto Tjandrawinata: Conceptualization, Methodology, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Molecular docking results

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Link: <https://doi.org/10.3897/pharmacia.73.e185272.suppl1>

Supplementary material 2

Molecular interactions

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